

DETERMINATION OF MOTIVATION TO ACHIEVE SUCCESS

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Annotatsiya. Muvaffaqiyat ko'pincha hayotdagi maqsadlaringizga erishish qobiliyati sifatida belgilanadi, bu maqsadlar qanday bo'lishidan qat'iy nazar. Muvaffaqiyat uchun yaxshiroq so'z qaysidir ma'noda erishish, muvaffaqiyat yoki taraqqiyot bo'lishi mumkin. Bu, albatta, maqsad emas, balki rivojlanish uchun zarur bo'lgan ko'nikmalar va resurslarni rivojlantirishga yordam beradigan sayohatdir.

Kalit so'zlar: taraqqiyot, shaxsiyat, motivatsiya, muvaffaqiyat, qadam, qobiliyat, ishonch, muvaffaqiyatsizlik, individual.

Аннотация. Успех часто определяют как способность достичь своих целей в жизни, какими бы они ни были. В некотором смысле, лучшим словом для обозначения успеха может быть «достижение», «достижение» или «прогресс». Это не обязательно пункт назначения, а путешествие, которое помогает развить навыки и ресурсы, необходимые для процветания.

Ключевые слова: прогресс, личность, мотивация, успех, шаг, способность, уверенность, неудача, индивидуальный.

Abstract. Success is often defined as the ability to reach your goals in life, whatever those goals may be. In some ways, a better word for success might be attainment, accomplishment, or progress. It is not necessarily a destination but a journey that helps develop the skills and resources you need to thrive.

Keywords: progress, personality, motivation, success, step, ability, confidence, failure, individual.

Introduction

The manifestation of individual initiative in society is one of the priority steps taken towards prosperity. The same initiative is one of the important phenomena for the state to find and develop progress. In the period of globalization and informatization processes of the present day, individual initiative is gaining momentum. The importance of personality awareness is expressed by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev can be noticed in his insistence that within the framework of "five important initiatives" - "it would certainly be beneficial if everyone acted with an appetite for a sense of Initiative".

Discussion and results

What is motivation?

This is a set of factors that motivate a person to work with a specific target direction. The concept of motivation is studied in socialism, biology and political science. Motivation is built around the needs of a person, and he seeks to satisfy them, he develops and grows, goes to the next stage of the hierarchy of needs. They are the main sources of human activity. This applies to both cognitive and practical activities.

Today, each of us needs success and self-confidence. How to achieve success, how to adapt to life circumstances that change every day, is it possible to somehow program luck?

Achieving success in 4 steps

Step 1

At first glance, the external features of success are usually recognized: good work, an apartment, an expensive car, summer residence, An Ordinary Family, Children and, of course, health. If we add to this the opportunity to go on vacation abroad, then we get a portrait of a person who is at the top of success. Some people achieve all this, but there is no sense of success, satisfaction. There are people who, despite the lack of money and various everyday problems, stubbornly go their own way and often win, because they remain themselves. The ability to harmonize with yourself and the world around you - this determines the success of real life.

Step 2

One of the prerequisites for success is to wait for changes and be morally prepared for them. People who want to succeed must learn to correctly solve failures, analyze them and learn from their wrong actions, not dramatization. If you can't analyze coldly, emotions have gone too far, then you need to think about how you can perceive what happened in a year or a few months. Perhaps in a week only one memory of the past failure will make you smile only. You should remember your achievements more often and not think about failures.

Step 3

Those who want to be successful must choose the right social circle. You need to communicate with energetic, active people, because each of us is subject to the influence of his environment. If losers dominate your social circle, they will pull you along with them, you yourself will not notice it either. Avoid such a circle of people, as well as people who will always agree with you, will approve of all the decisions you make.

Step 4

It is very important that you see yourself through the eyes of the people around you to understand how you are making an impression on others. If you have a rich imagination, then use it to build self-confidence by imagining yourself as a successful person who is respected by others. Try to accept the gestures, facial expressions and gait of someone you know. Means success. To perceive others and themselves as they are, to feel satisfaction from the walk towards the realization of their abilities.

The study of the phenomenon of individual initiative from a socio-psychological nature, the creation of a mechanism for its manifestation, is now one of the most pressing problems. In a study aimed at determining the place of tolerance in ensuring the socialization of the individual to society, as well as when tolerance was studied as the basis of the integration process, it was found that individual initiative has a special relevance. M. In initiative As Frese reasoned, the initiator insisted in the individual that goals were not given or assigned by someone else, but rather that these goals were developed by the individual himself.

Speaking about the qualities of an enterprising person, another characteristic necessary for society is leadership and the motivation of the individual has no choice not to speak. Initiative and leadership, we can see that there is a different approach in the study of these phenomena. In some studies, initiative is argued to be a leadership trait, and in others vice versa, leadership is argued to be an initiative personality trait, while in some studies, initiative and leadership are studied as personality phenomena.

Conclusion

It is very important for people whose motivation to "avoid failure" prevails to find an area of activity that will bring their psychophysiological predisposition to modern life, turning them into a positive result. A positive view of the world can be formed if you learn to change your

attitude towards what is happening and, accordingly, mobilize yourself for change. A person who has a superior motivation to avoid failure prefers a small, or, on the contrary, extreme risk, in which failure does not threaten reputation.

It usually has a high degree of protection and is afraid of accidents. And he is more likely to face such a problem. The predominance of the individual's motivation to avoid failure leads to low self-esteem and a level of aspiration. Repeated failures can lead such a person to a normal state of depression, a constant decrease in self-confidence and chronic fear of failure. Such people, as a rule, have a low level of development of achievement motivation. People with low motivation to succeed show that they are not confident in themselves and are imposed on what they are doing. Difficult tasks bother them.

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